

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN STATE REGULATION

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ABSTRACT: *The article discusses the importance of the digital economy, which is a modern requirement, and the benefits of its implementation in our country.*

KEYWORDS: *digital technology, digital economy, engineering, economics.*

The increase in the share of innovative activity has led to the fact that innovations are the same such as minerals, production capacity and intellectual capacity the country's wealth began to be counted. Our country and each of its citizens effective use of innovative and scientific and technical potential in the interests of formation of a multi-sectoral innovation policy in our country and its implementation to increase - there is no possibility without creating legal bases. The head of our state said, "... our country is an international information society. In 2019 according to the index of development of communication technologies although it has risen to the top, it is still far behind. Most ministries and agencies, It is also true that companies are far from digital technologies. Of course, Building a digital economy requires infrastructure, a lot of money and labor we know very well that it requires resources. However, no matter how difficult it is If we don't start work today, when will we start?! Tomorrow will be too late. To this end, active transition to the digital economy is one of our most important tasks in the next 5 years will be. The role of the digital economy in the economy in determining the competitiveness of countries in the process of globalization is unique. No matter which industry or sector of the economy we look at, we see the place of digital technologies in all of them. From services in the country's banking system, we can see the share of innovative digital technologies at the level of public services. The digital economy

is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is a modern stage of development, which is characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, but also reduces costs. At the same time, I am very worried and they are also effective in eliminating the most serious evil that bothers us - corruption is a tool. We all need to understand this deeply. State and community management, widely introducing digital technologies in the social sphere and increasing productivity, one in other words, people's lives can be dramatically improved." President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his appeals to the Oliy Majlis 202 declared the year as the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" Modernizing Uzbekistan today aims not only to develop, but to become one of the strongest countries as a result of comprehensive reforms implemented in various spheres of society. In the digital economy, information in digital form is the main element of production in all socio-economic areas, and the gradual transition to such an economic system will further increase the competitiveness of our country on a global scale, the quality of life of citizens, create new jobs, and enable rapid economic growth. creates and ensures national independence. In order to further develop the digital economy in our country, in order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 No. With the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 409 of June 25, 2020 "On measures to organize the activities of certain organizations within the system of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" at the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development The state institution "Digital Economy Research Center" was established. The main functions of the center are as follows:

- on the basis of comprehensive analytical and practical studies, to assess the impact of digitization processes on production and economic sectors, and to develop proposals for expanding the digital transformation of the country's economy in the future;

- to study and analyze the problems that arise in the wide implementation of the digital economy in the activities of state bodies and economic sectors, and to prepare comprehensively based proposals for their solutions;

- to study the experience of leading countries on the level of development of the digital economy and electronic government and to prepare proposals for their application to state bodies, organizations and economic sectors;

- formation of conceptual and methodological bases for the introduction of "smart" and other promising technologies, as well as large-scale data processing technologies in various sectors of the economy;

- development of long-term prospects for the development of electronic government and digital economy, based on the implementation of scientific and technical and research activities in the priority directions of the introduction of digital technologies.

In general, the Digital economy is a set of economic activities closely related to electronic business and electronic commerce based on digital technologies, as well as digital goods and services produced and sold as a result of this activity. The fact that the positions of deputy heads in the field of digitization have been introduced in the existing ministries and agencies in our country is also a factor in the development of the digital economy. According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and electronic government" by 2023, the share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product 2 and services in this field it is envisaged to increase the volume by 3 times, and to increase their export to 100 million dollars. Representatives of all spheres understand well that the widespread introduction of digital technologies can serve the development of the state and society, as well as the development of the social sphere, and can dramatically improve people's lives. Instead of conclusions and suggestions, it is worth saying that humanity is for development. It is clear only if it is carried out with the aim of making life easier the plan can be used. In the current period and near future of human development in terms of the quality of economic sectors,

social sphere and state management system development is directly related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies. The prospect of our country's development is the development of the digital economy and relies on the level of coverage of digital technologies. To achieve this the following basic conditions and priorities for the development of the digital economy it is appropriate to list the directions. It is no exaggeration to say that the literacy of the population is a step forward in this regard. It is the same in our country digital technology for public literacy at leisure. At the same time, the process of training specialists in this field is being strengthened. Leading specialists are currently lacking in digitization is also hindering; Number of activities of total schools in the field of secondary education. If we are not connected to technology, it is difficult to see the future towards a long digital life and hard work; an enterprise that is currently operating increasing the level of knowledge of employees, suitable for modern technical activities incentives that create a favorable opportunity for special tests or monthly salary. If we don't use it, we will separate the techniques in this field from the breath of the past we can't; Although the above suggestions may seem simple to you, they are actually ours that you and we can be the prelude to our foundation for future development we know well.

Some may wonder why the digital economy is needed and what it will provide. Digital economy does not mean only Blockchain technology and its use in international financial markets or cryptocurrencies. Of course, Blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies are also part of the digital economy. But the term "Digital Economy" refers to the economy conducted with the help of digital communications and IT. It can also be seen as a means of ending the underground economy. Because, firstly, all transactions must be registered electronically, and secondly, will be transparent. In addition, due to the use of new IT technologies in production, the cost of products and services will decrease.

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